

GROWTH STRATEGIES IN THE CHEMICALS AND ENERGY INDUSTRIES

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ABSTRACT

Internal (organic) growth, and external (inorganic) growth are the growth strategies adopted by the fast-paced chemicals and energy industries. Organic growth is achieved through investments in research and development (R&D), innovation, and capital expenditure (CAPEX) expansion. On the other hand, inorganic growth is a growth type that is realized through joint venture (JV) collaborations, and mergers and acquisitions (M&A) transactions. The effectiveness of the growth strategies is impacted by the global (macroeconomic) and the industrial (microeconomic) circumstances, which can be of two opposite effects in some geographies. These macroeconomic changes are due to global trade tensions, geopolitical unrest, energy prices fluctuation, and sustainability focus. In parallel, the microeconomic changes are due to lack of expertise availability, resources access, financial strength of companies, and market stability. Scientific, economic, financial, business, as well as strategy theories must be combined in a balanced interdisciplinary approach, as an important input to analyze and evaluate the strategies, which companies and the industry conducts.

Keywords: Business Strategy; Organic Growth, Inorganic Growth; Merger & Acquisition; Research and Development; Chemical Industry; Energy Industry.

1. INTRODUCTION

Strategy is not a synonym for success and should not be used as a substitute for “goal” or “plan”, as it should not be used to address a stand-alone decision, plan, or objective (Rumelt, 2013). Strategy is a cohesive and coherent set of actions, and policies that address high level objective or challenge (Rumelt, 2013). The chemical industry, which is highly energy-intensive, is closely related to the energy sector.

Oil, gas, coal, biomass, and forest woods are the main natural resources building blocks, that through additional processing are used to produce chemical products (American Chemistry Council, 2021). According to the American Chemistry Council (2021), these chemical products are used today for a wide range of applications including fuel blends, plastics, adhesives, pharmaceuticals, packaging, intermediates, and end-use products. The production processes in the chemical industry are characterized by complex transformations across the value chain (ICCA, 2024). The chemical industry is an industry that is driven by innovation, with significant amount of intellectual property (IP) developed over the years.

The chemical industry is continuously increasing in diversification, due to advancements in high-technology application sectors such as: nanotechnology, biotechnology, and specialty materials. In 2017, the chemical sector contributed \$5.7 trillion through direct, and indirect benefits, accounting for 7% of global world's gross domestic product (GDP). The chemical industry plays an important role in supporting—both directly and indirectly—120 million workforce job position globally (Oxford Economics & ICCA, 2019). In the coming decades, the chemical industry will continue to be crucial for the growth of manufacturing, construction, agriculture, energy, and transportation industries (Gocke, Rothman, & Schönberge, 2021).

Since 2000, and despite the market fluctuations, the chemical industry maintained lucrative earnings before interest, tax, depreciation, and amortization (EBITDA) margins, between 13% and 19% over the past 25 years (Yankovitz, Hardin, Kumpf, & Christian, 2024). Similarly, oil and gas companies experienced EBITDA margins ranging from 12% to 16.5% between 2011 and 2019 (IEA, 2020). Available academic literature offers limited insights into

internal (organic) growth and external (inorganic) growth strategies which are specific to the chemical and energy industries.

Financial indicators such as EBITDA margins, revenue, net profit, sales, and company's market capacity are used to describe growth performance. Nowadays, non-financial matrices such as employed workforce, geographical presence, employees' satisfaction, diversification, are important attributes contributing to growth potential and company's reputation.

Growth—following unconventional route—can be achieved by enhancing margins through cuttings costs, divesting, selling assets, and shrinking methods. The aim behind the followed approach is to minimize the bias toward any specific implemented strategy during the analysis, evaluation and conclusion development processes. On a global level, a lot of stakeholders can directly or indirectly benefit from this report and the subsequent future studies. The list is not limited to consultants, board members, policy makers, independent researchers, and investors.

2.REPORT METHODOLOGY

In this report, the focus is on internal (organic) and external (inorganic) growth strategies in the chemical and energy industries. Energy companies, under focus in this report, are specifically oil and gas companies, as they are related to the chemical industry, since they operate mainly in sectors upstream of the chemical industry. Green hydrogen companies, and developers are excluded from this study, as they have recently entered the energy market, have undergone a limited number of transactions, and are still under development. Additionally, companies involved in alternative energy production methods, such as solar, hydropower, electricity, wind, and nuclear energy, are omitted as they lack direct relevance to the chemical industry.

Both white and grey literature, encompassing qualitative and quantitative data, are critically analyzed, to extends beyond summarizing existing literature and avoid falling in publication bias. Grey literature input from organizational reports, consulting reports, articles, and official publications, are utilized in this report, as they are of a significant added value, complementing, and fulfilling part of the white literature gap.

Lack of data replicability, as well as low results reproducibility are not used as an exclusion criterion for utilized studies in this report. Differences in industrial contexts, geographical locations, market conditions, legal, and geopolitical inputs, might result in the choice and success of the applied growth strategy as an outcome variation.

To identify relevant resources, diverse research questions, and keywords combinations were used. More than 1340 results were identified—through an iterative research process—that were published between 1965 and 2025. Among the 1340 resources, 1231 were from databases and 109 were retrieved from the internet. They were identified with the help of different research engines, tools, and databases such as: Scopus, Google Scholar, Semantic Scholar, Scopus, OpenAlex, Lens, Elicit, and Litmaps. Initial screening, that skimmed the resource title, abstract, and conclusion, identified 115 relevant resources out of the 1340 resources. Reference check, known as forward and backward search, is performed to identify and analyze relevant research and publications, citing, and cited by the filtered sources, facilitated the identification of 10 additional resources, bringing the total number of retrieved resources to 125. From the 125 retrieved resources, 97 resources are cited in this report, which are divided into

71 academic (white) literature, and 26 professional (grey) literature. The remaining 28 resources (from the original 125) were not referenced, due to issues, such as repeated information, quality concerns, or due to the lack of added value to this report, as illustrated in the PRISMA flow chart (MJ et al., 2021) Figure 1.

Figure 1 PRISMA Flow Chart Identification of studies via databases and internet

3.BACKGROUND

3.1.THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Mergers and acquisitions (M&A) are important for organizational growth (Bauer & Matzler, 2014). M&A integration is defined as the degree of interaction and coordination between the two firms involved in a merger or acquisition (Larsson & Finkelstein, 1999). Steigenberger (2016) provided a conceptual framework to understand M&A integration. The research aimed to develop a more coherent understanding of the complex and fragmented nature of M&A (Steigenberger, 2016). By shifting the focus from a “yes/no” perspective to a “how” perspective, large companies across all industries, according to Rehm et al. (2012), rely on M&A for growth, with 75% of the top 500 companies worldwide actively engaging in M&A programs. The reason behind that most M&A transactions are small (systematic) deals, is that large M&A deals are relatively risky and require huge capital or debt (Rehm, Uhlaner, & West, 2012). Leveraging geopolitical agreements, international M&A activities are mainly driven by companies looking for access to skilled labor, raw materials, technology, and cost-effective markets presence.

Struggling to achieve the acquiring or merging company targets marks the M&A failure (Angwin, 2007; Martin, 2016; Uzelac, Bauer, Matzler, & Waschak, 2015). Large M&A deals, unlike small ones, have a less severe failure rate of approximately 10% (Bahreini, Bansal, Finck, & Firouzgar, 2019). Broader studies revealed that this percentage increased to be between 70% and 90% for the global M&A failure rate (Christensen, Alton, Risi, & Waldeck, 2011; Lev & Gu, 2024; Martin, 2016).

The integration success model emphasizes the combination and influence of synergy realization, organizational integration, and employee resistance (Larsson & Finkelstein, 1999). In the research titled “Post-Merger Integration: Hard Data, Hard Truths,” an 83% failure rate was reported for failing to meet one or more of the post-merger risk categories (Gerd, Strottmann, & Jayaprakash, 2010). Gerd et al. (2010) identified a set of 35 statistically significant risk factors that are used to determine the types of risk profiles, highlighting which factors are critical to assess before finalizing a deal. During

disruption and change periods, the M&A forecasts that were based on historical data, might not accurately predicts future performance (Perry & Herd, 2004). Gomes et al. (2013) demonstrated pre-and post-merger connections that lead to enhanced performance, and proposed framework for successful execution that defined motives, key performance indicators, and success factors as the primary components (Gomes, Angwin, Weber, & Tarba, 2013). Gomes et al. (2013) showed that clear and precise communication, regarding the management's intentions, and the company's strategy, are critical success factors, for both, pre-M&A and post-M&A phases. Further studies focusing on how human orientation, and interaction affect integration are recommended (Steigenberger, 2016).

Companies that have built internal M&A programs, and based on the market conditions, are actively carrying out M&A transactions, with the active participation of their internal M&A teams and M&A capabilities support (Aktas, Boone, Witkowski, Xu, & Yurtoglu, 2021). The study by Aktas et al. (2021) demonstrated how the M&A team can influence acquisition performance. Teams with strong financial expertise can be overconfident. This overconfidence can lead to filtering out and ignoring potential beneficial deals, before investing time in proper analysis. Strong financial skills can help them to choose the right method to value deals (Aktas, Boone, Witkowski, Xu, & Yurtoglu, 2021). Hiring external teams to be involved in the before and after acquisition stages, doesn't lead always to better results (Aktas, Boone, Witkowski, Xu, & Yurtoglu, 2021). Internal teams during these stages are just as effective. Companies that focus on real M&A goals and financial plans tend to experience larger returns than those that rely on feelings, satisfaction or opinions from the CEO and board (Aktas, Boone, Witkowski, Xu, & Yurtoglu, 2021).

According to Salvato et al. (2007), multiple M&A deals form internal company's knowledge-based experience. This knowledge will help them in creating better deals' strategies (Salvato, Lassini, & Wiklund, 2007). Rather than adhering to the same strategy each time, the advanced M&A strategies enabled these companies to diversify their approach, and integration methods (Salvato, Lassini, & Wiklund, 2007). According to Salvato et al. (2007), these companies have the advantage of documenting and archiving lessons learned, managerial practices, employee development, cultural integration, valuation models, and tools.

3.2. MARKET LANDSCAPE

The need for growth in the chemical and energy industries arises from the high complexity of the oil, gas, and chemicals business environment, which is driven by many factors across political, economic, ecological, societal, and technological landscapes (Vecchiato, 2012). Vecchio (2012) explores the huge changes that have taken place in the oil industry in the past thirty years. The industry is shaped by a lot of macroeconomic factors, that are difficult to be all managed at the same time (Vecchiato, 2012). The Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries, known as OPEC, began in 1960 in Iraq with the goal of assisting oil exporting countries to collaborate. After that, there were two wars in Iraq. Oil companies, owned by governments, that are established in the last decade, impacted the market power dynamics as well. After the fall of the Soviet Union, rising nationalism in countries like Russia and Venezuela, changed how the global oil industry works. Environmental concerns, economic downturns became more important. Lastly, the economic growth of Brazil, Russia, India, and China (BRIC) countries has influenced the market dynamics (Vecchiato, 2012).

China's investments, rising its chemical production capacity, result in capacity utilization and margin problems for the European chemical industry (Cefic, 2023). Between 2019 and 2023, and due to external economic factors, the European chemical plants only utilized about 75% of their capacity, which is as a drop compared to the 80% to 85% historical average (Cefic, 2023). As a result, many European chemical companies are reviewing their future operations, divestment and investment plans (Van Thienen, Broadhead, & Kalinkin, 2024). Van Thienen et al. (2024) argued that specialty chemicals industry in Europe has a better future than basic and commodity chemicals. The European chemical industry must stay competitive by focusing on specialty chemicals (Ronja et al., 2024). According to Van Thienen et al. (2024), specialty and fine chemical materials are produced from oil and gas. First, oil and gas are refined to produce petrochemicals. Petrochemicals are processed by chemical companies to produce base chemicals. In the last step, base chemicals are used to produce specialty chemicals. Several companies own and operate both upstream oil, gas and alternative energy assets, as well as downstream chemical plants.

The chemical industry is a global industry which is easily influenced by various micro- and macro-economic challenges and changes. It is evident that in Asian, Middle Eastern, and Eastern European countries, new competitors are appearing. On top of that, demand is not growing much. Energy prices levels are very high compared to pre-COVID and pre-Russian-Ukrainian war. Fossil fuels, and minerals raw materials are getting scarcer and more expensive. Environmental rules are becoming stricter and sustainability ambitions are widely announced. All these changes make it tough for chemical companies to make important decisions (Darkow & Von der Gracht, 2013; Van Thienen, Broadhead, & Kalinkin, 2024; Yankovitz, Hardin, Kumpf, & Christian, 2024).

Scenario simulating systems are developed by oil and gas, and chemical companies, such as Shell and BASF respectively, to help them in taking decisions, in an environment surrounded by global complex challenges. Shell employs global scenarios, while BASF utilizes global economic scenario management systems. In 2024, \$570 billion went into the oil and gas industries. This brings investment back to where it was in 2017 (IEA, 2024). Middle Eastern and Asian companies accounted for a significantly large share of the total global investments (IEA, 2024).

The effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on the chemical and energy industries resulted in turbulent conditions (Yankovitz, Hardin, Kumpf, & Christian, 2024). According to Yankovitz et al. (2024), the market conditions stemming from the pandemic lockdowns of 2020-2022 led to reduced demand and production, resulting in lowering overall revenues in 2020. In 2021 and 2022, after COVID-19 pandemic, the global chemical market recovered temporarily as a result of the increased demand. But in 2023 and 2024, world economy growth slowed down and manufacturing costs increased. That post pandemic effects decreased chemical companies' profit margins (Yankovitz, Hardin, Kumpf, & Christian, 2024).

Darkow et al. (2013) developed four different scenarios that studies different combinations of oil dependency and sustainability challenging pathways. Many experts think the scenario where the world depends heavily on oil but also focus on being sustainable is the most likely one (Darkow & Von der Gracht, 2013). According to Ronja et al. (2024) EU is advised to support R&D efforts to develop new sustainable products. This sustainability support presents a range of challenges and offers global transition opportunities (Ronja et al., 2024). Draghi et al. (2024) point out how important the chemical industry is for the European

economy as it play a rule in reducing the EU external dependencies. The European chemicals industry contributed €144 billion in 2021 to the EU economy (Draghi et al., 2024). Draghi et al. (2024) addressed the energy crisis in Europe. The International Energy Agency (IEA) estimates of the EU's fossil fuel energy import bill, rose from €341 billion in 2019 to €416 billion in 2023 (IEA, 2024). This underscores the necessity of transitioning the industry to hydrogen and green gases when they become cost-efficient (Draghi et al., 2024).

The interconnection between oil and gas energy companies and chemical companies is evident in various M&A deals, as well as divestment deals. INEOS bought British Petroleum's (Innovene) petrochemical business for \$9 billion (Morawietz & Herrmann, 2013). This transaction occurred one year after the establishment of Arkema in 2004, which resulted from the restructuring of Total's chemical business (Morawietz & Herrmann, 2013). BP and Total sold off their petrochemical and chemical businesses to focus on oil and gas businesses.

4. MERGER AND ACQUISITIONS (M&A) GROWTH STRATEGIES IN CHEMICAL AND ENERGY INDUSTRIES

4.1. M&A INDUSTRIAL CONTEXT

Mergers and acquisitions (M&A) are a powerful tool for corporate growth, yet they are often executed poorly. M&A should be viewed as a method to grow a portfolio rather than an end goal. Mergers and acquisitions (M&A) are considered the most significant lever for companies to enhance market share, generate value, and achieve cost efficiencies (IHS, 2016). M&A may sometimes be considered as a growth strategy when other growth strategies such as internal development, and licensing, are not suitable (Capron, 2016). Building, borrowing, and buying pathways decision questions offers a structured approach for selecting the right growth strategy. Capron (2016) stresses the importance of post-mergers and acquisitions integration, stating that companies need to successfully integrate the entity acquired in order to create value. If the market is stagnant or declining, M&A transactions can be the only possible option for companies looking for growth (Hay & Liu, 1988). Before taking a merger or acquisition decision, companies need to assess how well they can integrate a new entity. If companies cannot integrate a new entity, they should look for opportunities that require less integration effort (Capron, 2016).

According to Rashid et al. (2017), energy-intensive plants that are facing high energy costs, can lower their costs by utilizing M&A transactions for geographical expansions. Companies can fund their asset growth by divesting non-core assets. Mergers and acquisitions (M&A) can be a key for companies looking for expansions in the chemical industry. There are three types of mergers and acquisitions transactions: horizontal, vertical, and conglomerate (Rashid & Naeem, 2017). Horizontal and vertical mergers and acquisitions (M&A) occurs between companies that run businesses in the same industry. In vertical M&A, businesses at different levels in the supply chain, in the same

industry, join forces. Conglomerate M&A occurs when companies, that are present in different industries, combine.

Companies choose different M&A options to cut costs, grow their market share, and lower competition. Synergy creation is a primary goal in M&A activities in the petrochemical industries (Yoon, et al., 2008). Companies can achieve synergies through reallocation of resources, and elimination of duplicate activities (Yoon, et al., 2008).

Chemical companies' managers believe that good acquisition targets often have certain traits (Salvato, Lassini, & Wiklund, 2007). Companies with strong geographical presence, or the ones that owns solid market share, are attractive options for investors (Salvato, Lassini, & Wiklund, 2007). Companies acquiring other businesses doesn't mean they are ignoring organic growth opportunities. They can focus on both growth plans at the same time. According to Salvato et al. (2007), companies investing in acquisitions, achieved larger sizes than those that depended only on organic growth.

Chemical companies' business units (side businesses) that typically either generate low revenue or lack attention from management, are the attractive targets for private equity investments (McCauley, Scott, Taylor, Perr, & Bai, 2024). Cost synergies, that can be achieved in the market consolidation-driven deals, are a major incentive for PE funds. Kerisa's income massive increase by three times, after they bought the hygiene chemicals branch of the Roullier Group, is an example of successful acquisitions (McCauley, Scott, Taylor, Perr, & Bai, 2024). Singapore's sovereign wealth fund (GIC) partnered with the Carlyle Group, an American private equity firm, to acquire AkzoNobel Specialty Chemicals for \$10.1 billion, resulting in the formation of Nouryon (Nouryon, 2018).

4.2. M&A FINANCIAL IMPACT

Scholarly research analyzing the impact of mergers and acquisitions in the chemical and energy sectors are scarce and not frequently encountered. The impact of the merger and acquisition on the financial performance of a new chemical enterprise case study published by Yan (2024) investigates the

Economic Value Added (EVA) to evaluate the efficiency of the company. The EVA uses financial index methods to assess long-term results by focusing on economic profit. The research concludes that the transaction involving Jinfa Technology's acquisition of Baolai had a negative financial impact (Yan, 2024). Shick (1972) developed a method to figure out if mergers or acquisitions help the acquiring companies to earn more for their shareholders. He created a stock valuation model that demonstrated the success of the merger between Atlas Chemical and Air Products (Shick, 1972).

Mergers and acquisitions (M&A) activities are often driven by resource scarcity. One of the main drivers of foreign direct investment (FDI) is technology sourcing (Neven & Siotis, 1996). Kogut et al. (1991) employed a binomial regression model to estimate the effects of research and development (R&D) capability and industry structure on market interactions between the United States and Japan (Kogut & Chang, 1991). Additionally, Neven et al. (1996) developed an econometric model based on data from 1984 to 1989, utilizing Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression. Companies that create their own technologies like to set up new, fully owned branches. The goal is to prevent the spread of information (Neven & Siotis, 1996).

Mergers and acquisitions can play a significant role in restructuring declining industries (Sanjai, Shleifer, & Vishny, 1990). The study by Sanjai et al. (1990) analyzes post-expensive acquisitions (takeovers) and operational disruptions, including layoffs, tax savings, and investment reductions, to understand how these firms can justify the premium paid.

Deal closing in the chemical industry was difficult in 2022 and 2023. This can be explained by the high capital costs that was caused by rising inflation (McCauley, Scott, Taylor, Perr, & Bai, 2024). The difficult market conditions following the COVID-19 pandemic in 2023 and 2024 worsened the market conditions even more due to the high energy prices, particularly in Europe, as a direct consequence of the Russian-Ukrainian war. McCauley et al. (2024) demonstrated that these adverse circumstances affected mergers and acquisitions in the chemical industry. In 2023, the total value of these deals was \$102 billion, dropping over 50% from \$240 billion in 2018. The high number of M&A deals from 2014 to 2024 shows how attractive the industry is. In 2016, Dow and DuPont merged for \$130 billion. In 2017, ChemChina bought Syngenta for \$245 billion. In 2018, Bayer acquired Monsanto for \$63 billion, and Praxair and Linde combined for \$73 billion. In 2020, Aramco merged with SABIC for \$69.1 billion. In 2021, IFF bought part of DuPont's business for \$45.4 billion (McCauley,

Scott, Taylor, Perr, & Bai, 2024). The \$15.28 billion Covestro acquisition deal by ADNOC in 2024 (Covestro, 2024), along with the Aramco-SABIC deals from 2020, shows the diversification and integration strategies that oil and gas companies are employing.

These strategies aim to expand through vertical mergers and acquisitions (M&A) across both upstream and downstream sectors. In some countries like Japan, the market is structured in a way that oil and gas companies are completely separated from refining and chemical industries (Matsubara, 2019). This separation causes that either upstream or downstream industries are affected in a negative way during oil and gas price fluctuations. Chemical companies' profits decrease after the oil and gas prices rise (Matsubara, 2019). Some studies, during normal market conditions, uses M&A activities to predict oil returns and price volatilities (Bos, Demirer, Gupta, & Tiwari, 2018).

The Dow-DuPont merger was unique; it was a planned merger intended to be followed by a split within two years to enhance value, as well as to eliminate \$1.5 billion in corporate costs by integrating both companies into one entity before splitting it into three distinct companies, each focusing on a specific sector: Agriculture and Nutrition, Material Science, and Specialty Products (IHS, 2016). AkzoNobel and LG Chem made some big moves in the chemical industry by merging and acquiring other companies. In 2007, AkzoNobel bought Imperial Chemical Industries (ICI). This transaction helped AkzoNobel grow into a top company for coatings. Then in 2018, AkzoNobel sold their specialty chemicals business to a PE firm, that formed Nouryon. LG Chem formed a strategic alliance with Philips Electronics. After this deal, LG Chem became a top supplier of technology electronics (Morawietz & Herrmann, 2013).

Intellectual property (IP) constitutes a significant portion of a company's assets. Research and development (R&D) are essential for chemical companies to create new products and improve their current ones (Adetona, 2022). Mergers and acquisitions in the European chemical industry show how important it is to plan for intellectual property (Adetona, 2022). According to Adetona (2022), there are three main ways to value this kind of intellectual property. First, the income-based method. This looks at how much money the IP might make in the future. Second, the cost-benefit approach. This checks how much it would cost to create something similar. Lastly, the market-based way. IP value is determined in this method by comparing it with similar market transactions.

4.3. M&A FAILURE

M&A deals are a common strategy (Brouthers & Van Hastenburg, 1988). However, according to Brouthers et al. (1988), M&A deals are not successful in most of the cases. Brouthers et al. (1988) argues that relying solely on financial metrics, such as profitability, while neglecting other important objectives, is an inadequate measure of success.

Hercules (HPC) took on a lot of debt when it bought BetzDearborn. The \$2.4 billion deal in 1998 was a big failure (IHS, 2016). Ten years later, HPC was sold to Ashland. According to IHS (2016) report, big chemical companies started being more careful with mergers and acquisitions in the 2000s.

According to Davy et al. (1988), cultural compatibility is an important factor for a successful mergers and acquisitions (M&A). One-third to one-half of all M&A fail because of the challenges of integrating different cultures and teams (Davy, Kinicki, Kilroy, & Scheck, 1988). The research conducted by Davy et al. (1988) concludes that if communication during the M&A phases does not effectively address employees' concerns, it can lead to decreased productivity, foster a negative work environment, increase turnover rates, and create obstacles that hinder the achievement of merger goals. Brouthers et al. (1988) argues that economic goals, personal reasons, and following strategic plans are the three main drivers for managers to choose M&A as a growth strategy.

4.4. M&A GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS AND GLOBAL DEALS

European companies focus more on international M&A deals (Ornaghi, Marín, & Siotis, 2004). European businesses invest in North American businesses more than what North American businesses invest in Europe. Europe and North America have a similar mix of vertical and horizontal M&A deals in the chemical industry. The numbers are almost the same in both regions. They focus a lot on sectors like pharmaceuticals and biotechnology. They do this to maintain and expand their knowledge (Ornaghi, Marín, & Siotis, 2004).

Since 1990, the chemical industry in Europe has changed a lot. As a result, clear boundaries between different industries were set, due to demand shifts, and R&D declining returns.

Because of these boundaries, companies had to change their setup. That move, created new companies in the biotechnology, and pharmaceuticals sectors (Walsh & Lodorfos, 2002).

Fragmented markets have lots of small competitors with unstable profits. These small businesses are often ambitious. They are looking for reaching larger market share (McCauley, Scott, Taylor, Perr, & Bai, 2024). In new emerging markets, joining forces through consolidation will remain being a significant driving force in the chemical and energy industries (Morawietz & Herrmann, 2013). An analysis of 500 mergers and acquisitions in the global chemical industry from 2016 to 2020, totaling \$300 billion, found that 44% were driven by portfolio extensions. Consolidation transactions accounted for 29% of the deals. New regions expansions counted for 15% of the deals. M&A in new business areas comprised 12% (Elser, Walczyk, & Bjacek, 2021). From 2012 to 2022, the M&A deals totaled \$1.1 trillion (Elser, Bjacek, & Walczyk, 2022; Deloitte, 2023). Private equity invested \$97.8 billion. An impactful 9% of the chemical industry \$1.1 trillion deals.

Mergers and acquisitions in the oil and gas industry are quite common. The \$54 billion acquisition of BG Group by Shell, which created the world's largest liquefied natural gas (LNG) business, was analyzed by Kalam (2021) to quantify the effects of the transaction on the financial performance of both companies. According to Kalam (2021), the deal could help Shell save about \$3.5 billion each year. This means that Shell could rely less on oil and boost its oil and gas production by 20%. This merger increased the valuation of both companies (Kalam, 2021). When the news came out, Shell's BG Group's stock value rose significantly.

From 1958 to 1965, the American oil and refining business expanded via mergers and acquisition (Strieber, 1968).

In China, the government developed a plan called "Made in China 2025." This plan is developed to motivate Chinese businesses to improve their international market position (Lopacinsk, 2017). Chinese companies focus on buying chemical companies in Europe, and are investing heavily in Brazilian and Russian firms (Lopacinsk, 2017; Rodionova, Chernyaev, & Korenevskaya, 2017). This plan promotes international acquisitions by Chinese companies and encourages them to become global leaders (Lopacinsk, 2017). Between 1990 and 2013, most chemical mergers and acquisitions happened between companies in the same

area. Companies in Europe and the U.S. are not very active in international deals outside their geographies. In contrast, Chinese companies are more active in these deals (Morawietz & Herrmann, 2013). Rodinova et al. (2017) claim that BRICS countries work closely in energy and chemicals sectors. Chemical companies are partnering up to grow in Asia and the Middle East (Morawietz & Herrmann, 2013). Lodorfos et al. (2006) suggest a four-step approach to manage cultural integration. First, the pre-merger stage. In this stage companies use job rotations and retreats to identify the cultural differences. Second, the planning stage. During this step, companies develop plans. Third, the implementation step. This is when the structural and control systems are integrated. The last step is the evaluation stage. Here, companies look at their plans and see how the actual results are (Lodorfos & Boateng, 2006).

M&A deals show how fast changes occur in the European manufacturing sector. In the 1960s and 1970s, companies used to merge in order to diversify. But in the 1980s and 1990s, the attention shifted to the focus on core businesses (Chapman & Edmond, 2000). The merger and acquisition (M&A) between Hoechst and Rhone-Poulenc resulted in the formation of Aventis as a new entity (Regulation (EEC) No 4064/89 Merger Procedure, 2004). This deal was a result of both companies' desires to have a better competitive position in the European market. M&A or divestiture decisions that were planned to be made by state-owned companies, are mostly re-assessed by the new acquiring company's management. The implementation of substantial job cuts, which may be politically challenging for the state-owned company management, can be transferred to a foreign entity through acquisition (Chapman, 1988). Selling state-owned businesses to private companies helped them grow in new areas. They became more attractive for being a cross border investment and an M&A target (Chapman, 1988). Cross-border M&A are crucial for the EU industry restructure (Chapman & Edmond, 2000).

Companies evaluate the M&A transaction hard and soft factors (Mustaffa, 2017). Hard factors evaluated are due diligence and synergy opportunities. M&A soft factors include maintaining employee motivation and effective communication. It also covers evaluating teams' integrations and plans for keeping skills (Mustaffa, 2017). Lack of communication, from the top management to the lower levels, resulted in the absence of an integrated plan prior to the change process in the merger transaction between Henkel South Africa and National Starch Adhesives (Ntobongwana, 2009).

5. INTERNAL (ORGANIC) GROWTH STRATEGIES IN CHEMICAL AND ENERGY INDUSTRIES

5.1. INDUSTRIAL R&D CONTEXT

The chemical industry is one of the most advanced manufacturing sectors. It is based on intense research and development. The industry is advanced within developed economies. It adds to the gross domestic product (GDP) and supports growth (Arora, Landau, & Rosenberg, 2000).

Patents keep ideas and inventions safe. Innovations can find new applications for existing products. They are tools to create new materials and invent manufacturing techniques (Elser, Walczyk, & Bjacek, 2021). Innovation provides companies with competitive advantages. It allows them to make new products or improve the existing ones. The main purpose of innovation is to create value for businesses and to help them operate efficiently (Taques, López, Basso, & Areal, 2020). The innovation process starts with an input stage. Here, companies define the scope, and structure. This is followed by an intermediate stage. The main goal of this stage is to protect the intellectual property. The output stage can be unpredictable and uncontrollable, resulting in the production of new products and the generation of incremental revenue (Taques, López, Basso, & Areal, 2020).

The chemical industry is fundamentally based on continuous development, research, and innovative chemistry, which facilitates the creation of new products (Marsch, 2008). The German chemical industry grew significantly between 1850 and 1860. Decentralized R&D structures in the German chemical industry enhanced the growth of the after 1990 (Marsch, 2008).

Chemical companies that focus on innovation have the agility to adapt to markets that are changing in a fast pace. By adapting this strategy, they can stay competitive (Yankovitz, Hardin, Kumpf, & Christian, 2024). Middle managers have the largest responsibility in implementing organic growth strategies (McGrath, 2009).

R&D efforts, within the chemical industry, have led to the creation of engineering plastics. Engineering plastics' mechanical and thermal properties are developed to be better than that of the commodity plastics (Ceresana, 2021). According to the Ceresana (2001) report, engineering plastics are defined as materials used in applications that replace traditional materials like ceramics, glass, and metals. Engineering plastics are more efficient than traditional materials for complex shapes manufacturing. They can reduce the market's reliance on other minerals.

Hall et al. (2009) conclude that there is a significant link between research and development (R&D) investments and growth in the chemical industry, arguing that the social returns on R&D are typically higher than the private returns. When a company invests in R&D, there is a probability that other companies can benefit from that knowledge. R&D group, and the company IP system administrator, have the responsibility to prevent knowledge spillovers by protecting their patents, and securing their innovation (Hall, Mairesse, & Mohnen, 2009). For instance, synthetic fiber was originally developed by the chemical industry and later utilized in applications by the textile industry. Like other physical assets, non-tangible assets, such as the R&D knowledge, depreciates. The depreciation rate is approximately 18% for chemical companies in the private sector (Hall, Mairesse, & Mohnen, 2009; Bernstein & Mamuneas, 2006). Chemical companies can achieve 25% return on investment (Link, 1981).

Arora et al. (2004) examined the impact of corporate restructuring in the chemical industry on research and development (R&D) (Arora, Ceccagnoli, & Da Rin, 2004). Arora et al. (2004) argued that changes in debt and cash flow drive the focus on short-term results. After companies go through changes in structure, they normally re-identify new R&D key performance indicators (KPIs). This restructuring can increase R&D investments.

Companies investing in R&D in the chemical industry can choose between two strategy options, an escalation strategy and a propagation strategy (Marín & Siotis, 2004). In the first option, they can focus their R&D efforts on a single product, in an escalation strategy. Companies spread their R&D efforts over many products, when they adopt the propagation strategy. Marín et al. (2004) anticipated observing the escalation strategy (concentration of R&D efforts) in segments of the chemical industry where there are higher degrees of substitutability among product varieties. Companies need to keep their

strategies during tough economic times. If they are working on developing a new product, they shouldn't decrease their R&D expenditure to improve their cash flow. That reduction can cause them more problems in the future (McLinn, Paepe, & Schottland, 2017).

Based on the European patents filed at the European Patent Office (EPO) between 1986 and 1997, chemical companies primarily conduct their research within their home countries, with an average of only 11.6% of patents being developed overseas. This results in 86% of their chemical research activities being concentrated in Europe (Mariani, 2004). The top 20 chemical industry areas in Europe hold 77.5% of all patents. Large companies help international inventors work together. They can create more interdisciplinary patents than smaller companies (Mariani, 2004).

There are three main strategies in the chemicals industry (McLinn, Paepe, & Schottland, 2017). First, companies can focus on being the low-cost provider. Second, they can create unique products by investing in R&D. Third, they can focus on providing great customer service. McLinn et al. (2017) concluded that none of these major strategies is inherently superior to the others. Companies' executives need to respond to the changing chemicals market and to stick to a strategy while being agile. It is important to invest in their skilled employees and leverage their strength. McLinn et al. (2017) indicate that outperforming chemical companies that focus on investing in their core markets achieve better financial results than those that choose to venture into new markets.

The market structure, competition, and innovation in the chemical industries of Europe and the United States are quite similar across the Atlantic (Marín & Siotis, 2004). European and North American companies are leading R&D investments in the energy industry (Rodionova, Chernyaev, & Korenevskaya, 2017). Western European and North American oil and gas companies have higher internationalization of their R&D activities compared to the Russian and Chinese companies (Lobov & Rybin, 2022). The oil and gas industry ranks the second lowest industry that invest in R&D (Matkovskaya, Vechkinzova, Petrenko, & Steblyakova, 2021). Oil and gas companies invest 0.3% of their earnings into R&D. Oil and gas companies are spending more on research and development lately. Asia's contribution to the R&D investments in the energy industry is mainly by China, India, and Japan. These oil and gas Asian companies invest 37% the global R&D (Rodionova, Chernyaev, & Korenevskaya, 2017). Management believes that not much needs to be changed in the oil and gas

industry (Matkovskaya, Vechkinzova, Petrenko, & Steblyakova, 2021). Since they are making good profits and have strong market power, they feel their position is safe. This resulted in having low R&D levels.

R&D in the energy industry aims to reduce the costs of alternatives to fossil fuels. This increases the competitiveness of biofuels, solar, hydro, wind, and maybe hydrogen energy sources.

5.2. INTERNAL VS. EXTERNAL R&D

Dahab et al. (1994) argue that large firms have an edge in innovation. Big companies normally have a solid reputation. On the other hand, small companies struggle more with innovation (Dahab & Teixeira, 1994). Governmental R&D centers may not be very effective (Dahab & Teixeira, 1994). External collaborations between companies and universities are secondary, as firms remain the primary focus of operations (Dahab & Teixeira, 1994). In contrast, Narula (2001) observes that technology-driven companies are increasingly utilizing non-internal R&D methods. They invest in licensing, partnerships, and outsourcing. This shift towards non-internal R&D is due to their reduced risks and lower capital requirements compared to internal R&D activities. However, depending on external R&D activities can have major drawbacks (Narula, 2001). Therefore, they are still not very commonly adopted by companies.

Striking the right balance between internal and external R&D activities is crucial for companies to maintain long-term competitiveness, as smaller firms often have limited resources. These limitations are important considerations when selecting alliances and non-internal R&D strategies (Narula, 2001).

Arora et al. (2020) argues that many companies find it hard to turn their R&D effort to be profitable. Big companies are shifting their attention to focus on business development and sales instead of focusing on internal R&D. Accordingly, it is getting harder to turn scientific findings into products (Arora, Belenzon, Patacconi, & Suh, 2020). Big companies can integrate different types of knowledge, share risks, and focus on solving challenges. In contrast,

university research is mostly based on curiosity. It is clear that companies and research institutes have different goals (Arora, Belenzon, Pataconi, & Suh, 2020). If universities want to turn their R&D to be profitable, they need to change their business model and how they do research.

M&A between companies with similar technologies help R&D synergies (Cassiman, Colombo, Garrone, & Veugelers, 2005). Transactions involving similar technologies produce less R&D outcomes, as a result of decreasing R&D investments. As the market is saturated and R&D profits are declining, chemical companies shifted their focus toward higher value-added products (Walsh & Lodorfos, 2002). Petrochemical companies have plans to safeguard their innovations. This is done through creating entry barriers, patents, product modifications, learning from mistakes, scaling, and vertical integration (Dahab & Teixeira, 1994). Companies create spin-offs to divest these newly-established parts of their business (Festel, 2014). R&D spin-outs can help speed up innovation in case they focus on shorter time to market, and commercialization (Festel, 2014). Companies can choose for shrinking to achieve sustainable profitability (Charles River Associates, 2021).

Technology and innovation are getting more complicated. This makes it tough for chemical companies like DuPont to use patents and technologies from other countries, like the UK (Arora, Ceccagnoli, & Da Rin, 2004). According to Arora et al. (2004), this situation shows the necessity for companies to develop their own technical capabilities internally.

In the biopharmaceutical industry, a branch from the chemical industry, that is considered a knowledge-based industry, researchers created a framework that studies how R&D funding is affected after an M&A (Miozzo, DiVito, & Desyllas, 2015). Miozzo et al. (2015) found that multinational, science-based companies allocate higher R&D investments in their home country, where their headquarters are located, compared to their investments in other countries where they operate. Companies' IP, and ties to universities give them a market advantage (Arora, Belenzon, Pataconi, & Suh, 2020; Miozzo, DiVito, & Desyllas, 2015). This advantage, according to Miozzo et al. (2015), enhances their ability to improve their technological capabilities, and to attract investments. State-owned enterprises, national private institutions, and foreign corporations have driven growth in the Brazilian petrochemical sector (Dahab & Teixeira, 1994). However, this growth has also led to numerous small, technologically stagnant firms (Dahab & Teixeira, 1994). Aramco, invest in building their own R&D centers, and

collaborate with universities and R&D centers (Abdul Fasi, 2024). Aramco's R&D investments resulted in 7,718 patents in oil, gas and chemical sectors by 2021. Most of them were registered in the United States (Abdul Fasi, 2024).

5.3. FINANCIAL DOMAINS

Intellectual Capital (IC) is a part of the non-physical assets owned by a company. This includes knowledge, research, skills, and information systems (Abdolmohammadi, 2005). Abdolmohammadi (2005) conducted research that developed a regression model to quantitatively assess the relationship between the dependent variables while controlling for other factors that could influence market capitalization. There is a strong positive correlation between the disclosure of intellectual capital (IC) in the annual reports of Fortune 500 companies and their market capitalization (Abdolmohammadi, 2005). Total Shareholder Return (TSR) is an important financial metrics that affect investor decisions. The TSR of the chemical industry ranks it in the 13th place among the large industries (Gocke, Rothman, & Schönberge, 2021). Chemical companies worth over \$7 billion reached an annual TSR of 12% from 2011 to 2020. Those with a value above \$1 billion had a 9.1% annual return (Gocke, Rothman, & Schönberge, 2021). These rates are better than the average growth of 11% for large companies in all industries.

The growth in the chemical industry relates to how much money is spent on new ideas and improvements (Elser, Walczyk, & Bjacek, 2021). Specialty chemical companies lead the top 10% chemical companies (Gocke, Rothman, & Schönberge, 2021). They achieved financial performance results better than what base chemicals, basic plastics, and fertilizers companies have reached. This shows that investing in R&D is a good move. Specialty chemical companies spend more on research and development than other chemical firms. This helps them stay ahead and grow their business. Multispecialty, and base chemical companies, focus on capital spending, and operational excellence to grow. The return difference, between companies manufacturing commodity chemicals and those producing specialty chemicals, fell from 10% to 3%. This occurred because commodity chemical companies are working on improved operations, and using digital tools applications. They (commodity chemical companies) are

gradually moving away from selling basic products (Gocke, Rothman, & Schönberge, 2021).

Enterprise value (EV) is calculated by adding market cap and total debt minus the available cash. The EV/EBITDA ratio shows a gap between the best and worst companies in the chemical market (Charles River Associates, 2021). There are six key characteristics that drive the performance of leading companies. Focusing on technology and shaping portfolio coherence. Having a distinct leadership position. Managing choices effectively. Operating in an attractive market structure, following a robust growth plan, and having relatively stable performance. Charles River Associates (2021) analyzed over 70 publicly traded chemical companies that worth over \$10 billion. These companies either follow a growth plan or are present in markets that are growing fast. Top 10 performing companies had an EV/EBITDA multiple of 19x, compared to a market average of 12x. Between 2016 and 2020, the top 10 companies reached 29% annual return for their shareholders. During the same period the market average was at 14% (Charles River Associates, 2021).

5.4. PRIVATE AND PUBLIC COMPANIES R&D FOCUS

The research on financial innovation posits that a company's capital structure is critical to its innovation outcomes (Kerr & Nanda, 2015). According to Kerr et al. (2015), the relationship between public equity markets and innovation varies across different industries. It depends on company's financial structure and its dependence on outside funding. They emphasize that bank financing and public equity markets are vital funding sources for established companies that rely on external capital (Kerr & Nanda, 2015).

In a study examining whether public and private firms behave differently in the chemical industry, Sheen (2019) analyzed investment behavior in the U.S. commodity chemical sector between 1989 and 2006. Private companies are usually better at knowing when to invest than public ones. When prices and demand are expected to go up, they increase their production. But before even demand drops, they slow down expansion. They also keep an eye out for acquisition opportunities during tough periods (Sheen, 2019). Conversely, Sheen (2019) notes that public firms often fall into traps of time-to-build delays

and demand over-extrapolation, as well as relying on past demand to inform future investment decisions, which can result in poorly timed choices.

6.SUSTAINABILITY AND PRACTICALITY

Ananda et al. (2008) argued that investing in energy and materials sustainable alternatives is a financial burden for lots of companies and communities.

Developing sustainable alternatives requires resources, significant investments, and substantial changes to operational, innovative, and financial models.

Australian chemical industry can enhance its competitiveness by developing environmentally sustainable chemical products. The Australian government can help in this transition by providing companies with financial incentives (Ananda, Domazetis, & Hill, 2008).

The relationship between sustainability and firm value, can be explained by two opposing theories (Denuwara et al., 2022). First, the “value-creating” theory. According to which, sustainability may reduce risk and enhance long-term value. Second, the “value-destroying” theory. The theory states that investing in sustainability might harm shareholders, as it can divert companies’ attention from focusing on their core activities (Denuwara et al., 2022). Ezekoye et al. (2022) found that investors worry about cash flow and returns on their investments. Some of the investors do not care whether their companies are on the Dow Jones Sustainability Index (DJSI) or not, as they believe that being listed does not improve company’s valuation or profit. However, green chemicals companies are more likely to protect future cash flow (Ezekoye, Lavandier, Lorbeer, Rehm, & Wallach, 2022). Yet, Ezekoye et al. (2022) found that investors do not think that there is a connection between how well they are doing financially, and whether they have met their environmental, social, and governance (ESG) goals.

Companies that develop sustainable products bring new opportunities for the whole market (Elser, Walczyk, & Bjacek, 2021). This emphasizes that innovation has led to the creation of new products over the past century, such as nylon and polyurethane, which have benefited various other industries (Elser, Walczyk, & Bjacek, 2021). Breakthrough innovations, and incremental innovations, create new products, and improve existing ones, respectively. Improving available

materials is often less risky for R&D investments. Incremental innovations usually have faster and more reliable financial returns if they are compared to breakthrough innovations. Elser et al.'s (2021) analysis of 2,600 industry capital expenditure (CAPEX) projects from 2016 to 2020, revealed that 68% of these projects and 73% of mergers and acquisitions (M&A) announcements aimed to expand the existing range of chemical products in traditional sectors, including fertilizers, basic and intermediate chemicals, and thermoplastics.

Major oil producers have invested in biofuel production by collaborating with U.S. universities. Their objective is to generate profit or, at the very least, to gain a deeper understanding of the production of ethanol, methanol, liquid fuels, and other chemicals derived from biomass (Sheridan, 2007). Private investors and venture capitals, invest in small companies that are developing biofuels from biomass. Those efforts by venture capitalists and major oil producers, aim to address and capture market share, in alignment with the 2030 U.S. target announced in the early 21st century, which seeks to replace 30% of gasoline with biofuel by 2030 (Sheridan, 2007). However, there are many obstacles that faces biofuel scaling (Vertès, Inui, & Yukawa, 2006). The technology must be developed further to be economically viable, and geopolitical situations must be filtered out of the equation.

7.GAPS IN THE REPORT

The report is limited by the public accessible information in white and grey literature. The study period was restricted to the years between 1965 and 2025. There is a scarcity of published academic work about the balance between organic and inorganic growth strategies in the chemical and energy markets. The energy resources in this report are limited to oil and gas as they are linked to the chemical industry. This focus is further supported by the fact that many oil and gas companies rebranded themselves during and after the COVID-19 pandemic as energy companies, rather than being solely fossil fuel-based. There is a notable lack of comparative case studies in the chemicals and energy industries, that assess and compare situations before and after the implementation of growth strategies. There is not much research on how companies can combine both strategies effectively.

8.CONCLUSION

Companies are working to keep their market positions and, preferably, to improve their market share. In order to reach this goal, some companies choose a growth strategy, or combination of strategies, to adapt with changing conditions of the market. There is a scarcity of academic publications on the balance between internal—R&D and capex expansion—growth strategies, and external—M&A and joint venture—growth strategies in the chemicals and energy industries. Public reports, that address both strategies, are mostly published by consulting firms and international organization, and consequently they form the main narrative in this field.

The aim is to improve the understanding of internal research and development (R&D) or capacity growth compared to mergers and acquisitions (M&A) as strategies for expansion within the chemical and energy sectors.

Correlation between the growth strategies different variables, do not always indicate their causation factor in their successes or failures. How, and why, strategy practices, in the chemicals and energy industries, are shaped in the way they are today, as well as analyzing the long-term impact of adopting a certain strategy can be the basis for future studies. Future studies could also look at how the general industry experience, and companies' financial status impact strategy choice, as well as their successes, among other factors.

When a company decides to grow, it is limited by how much risk it can handle, as well as their financial situation. Companies, with large resources, can allocate resources to balance between steady organic growth, while looking for good external growth chances.

Companies should stay flexible with their long-term plans, but also focus their short-term plans on the basics of their industry, and on what they are good at today. If companies do not adopt a short and a long-term strategy, they can get sidetracked by trends and industrial hypes. These hypes and trends promoted by consulting agencies, reports, think tanks, lobbies, conferences, celebratory sustainability announcements, are based on selective definitions of clean energy sources, as well as being politically influence. This renewed focus should honor scientific principles and market dynamics.

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